

Sample Name: PP UV <1 μm

Material: Polypropylene

Size: <1 μm

Production Partner: TNO

Storage Conditions: Refrigerated and dark

Summary

Physical Characteristics

- Median diameter (D_{50,v}) = 1,62 μm
- Particles have an irregular morphology
- 4,4 x10¹² particles per gram
- 40299 cm²/g surface area

Chemical Characteristics

- >99% C₃H₆ (PP) determined by XRF
- C=O peak (1713 cm⁻¹) due to oxidation observed in FTIR spectrum
- Not able to obtain a cathodoluminescence spectrum

Description of terms

- D[4,3]:Volume mean (μm)
- D[3,2]:Surface area mean (μm)
- D[2,1]: Spherical particle mean (μm)
- D[1,0]: Number length mean (μm)
- D_{50,v}: Median diameter (volume basis, μm)
- D_{50,N}: Median diameter (number basis, μm)
- N_w: Number of particles per gram plastic (#/g)
- A_w: Surface area of particles per gram plastic (cm²/g)

Particle Size Distribution (using Static Light Scattering (SLS) provided by TNO)

D[4,3]	D[3,2]	D[2,1]	D[1,0]	D50 _N	D50 _V	N _w	A _w
1,90	1,31	0,73	0,40	0,24	1,62	4.4 x10 ¹²	40299

Chemical Composition (using XRF provided by Malvern Panalytical)

Chemical formula	Concentration (%)
C_3H_6	99,937
Element	Concentration (ppm)
Si	227
P	73
S	10
Cl	449
K	54
Ca	88
Ti	3
Cr	83
Mn	4
Fe	223
Ni	15
Cu	1
Zn	1
Mo	1
Pb	1

Chemical Bonding (Using μ -FTIR provided by TNO)

Cathodoluminescence Spectroscopy (*provided by TNO*)

Not available